

Synthesis and Plant Growth Retardant Activity of Trialkylammonium Iodides derived from Citronellal

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Citronellal is converted to *N,N*-dimethyl-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enylamine by Leukart reaction and citronellyl bromide is converted to *N,N*-diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-oct-6-enylamine by refluxing with diethylamine, K_2CO_3 and acetone. These tertiary amines after having been modified at the double bond are converted to quaternary salts of ammonia by treating them with methyl and ethyl iodides. All the compounds have been tested as plant growth retardants on the hypocotyl cuttings of *Vigna radiata*.

In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis and plant growth retardant activity of some quaternary salts of ammonia derived from citral and citronellal^{1,2}, the present work was undertaken to prepare thirteen new quaternary salts of ammonia in which epoxy, dichloromethylene, methoxy and tertiary carbinol groups are introduced at the double bond of the citronellal and tested as plant growth retardants on the hypocotyl cuttings of *Vigna radiata*.

Methanolic solution of *N,N*-dimethyl-3,7-dimethyl-6-octenylamine (1) was treated with freshly crystallised mercuric acetate dissolved in methanol and methanolic solution of KOH, followed by solid sodium borohydride to get *N,N*-dimethyl-3,7-dimethyl-7-methoxyoctanylamine (3) in good yield. Similarly, *N,N*-diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-7-methoxyoctanylamine (4) was prepared from the corresponding *N,N*-diethylamine (2).

The dialkylamines 1 and 2 dissolved in chloroform when treated with aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide in presence of catalytic amount of triethylbenzylammonium chloride³ produced *N,N*-dimethyl-6,7-dichloromethylene-3,7-dimethyloctanylamine (6) and *N,N*-diethyl-6,7-dichloromethylene-3,7-dimethyloctanylamine (7) respectively, in good yield. The unsaturated dialkylamines (1 and 2) were also epoxidised with one equivalent of perbenzoic acid⁴ in dry chloroform to yield *N,N*-dimethyl-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epoxyoctanylamine (8) and *N,N*-diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epoxyoctanylamine (9) respectively. 2 on mercuration-demercuration⁵ yielded *N,N*-diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-7-hydroxyoctanylamine (5).

The methoxy, dichloromethylenes, epoxides and tertiary carbinols thus prepared were confirmed from their nmr spectra and elemental analyses. The dialkylamines (3-9) were converted to the corresponding ammonium iodides (10-22) by treating them with methyl and ethyl iodides in dry

ether. The compounds were tested on *Vigna radiata* and the effect of different concentrations of these compounds on number of roots per rooted segments produced on hypocotyl cuttings was noted. Epoxy quaternary ammonium compounds (14, 16 and 17) were found to be strong inhibitors which inhibit both ep cotyl elongation as well as root initiation of hypocotyl cuttings, whereas the dichloromethylene derivative of quaternary ammonium salt (11) was found to have inhibitory effect at higher concentration (10-20 ppm). Hydroxy quaternary ammonium salt (22), was found to have slight promotory effect at the lower concentration and toxic at higher concentration.

1 ; R = R' = CH₃
2 ; R = R' = C₂H₅

3 ; R = R' = R'' = CH₃
4 ; R = R' = C₂H₅, R'' = CH₃
5 ; R = R' = C₂H₅, R'' = H

6 ; R = R' = CH₃
7 ; R = R' = C₂H₅

8 ; R = R' = CH₃
9 ; R = R' = C₂H₅

- 10; R = R' = CH₃, R'' = C₂H₅
 11; R = R' = CH₃, R'' = C₂H₅
 12; R = R' = C₂H₅, R'' = CH₃
 13; R = R' = R'' = C₂H₅

- 14; R = R' = R'' = CH₃
 15; R = R' = CH₃, R'' = C₂H₅
 16; R = R' = C₂H₅, R'' = CH₃
 17; R = R' = R'' = C₂H₅

- 18; R = R' = R'' = CH₃
 19; R = R' = C₂H₅, R'' = R''' = CH₃
 20; R = R' = R'' = C₂H₅, R''' = CH₃
 21; R = R' = C₂H₅, R'' = CH₃, R''' = H
 22; R = R' = R'' = C₂H₅, R''' = H

Experimental

Boiling and melting points are uncorrected. Drying of all organic extracts was done over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Purity of analytical samples was checked by thin layer chromatography. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were taken on a EM360/390 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

N,N-Dimethyl-3,7-dimethyl-7-methoxyoctanylamine (3): A solution of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate (9.6 g) in methanol (15 ml) was added with stirring at 5–10° to the amine (1; 5.67 g) dissolved in methanol (45 ml). After stirring for 30 min at this temperature, a solution of KOH (4.6 g) in methanol (50 ml) was added and solid sodium borohydride (400 mg) was then added immediately in small portions. The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h, filtered and the filtrate concentrated to half the volume under reduced pressure. It was then diluted with water (70 ml) and extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed with water, dried and residue after removal of solvent was chromatographed over silica gel to furnish 3 (70%; 4.0 g) (Found: C, 72.64; H, 13.42; N, 6.60. C₁₅H₂₉NO requires: C, 72.55; H, 13.48; N, 6.51%); δ 2.06–2.16 (8H, m, (CH₂)₂CH(OCH₃)₂, CH₂, N(CH₃)₂) and 3.40 (3H, s, OCH₃).

N,N-Diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-7-methoxyoctanylamine (4): It was prepared as described above from 6.53 g of N,N-diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-6-octenylamine (2) in 75% yield (Found: C, 74.0; H, 13.64; N, 5.84. C₁₅H₂₉NO requires: C, 74.07; H, 13.58; N, 5.76%); δ 1.05–1.26 (18H, m, (CH₂)₂CH(OCH₃)₂, saturated methylenes, (CH₂)₂C(OCH₃)₂).

N,N-Diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-7-hydroxyoctanylamine (5): 2 (4 g) was added with stirring at room

temperature to a solution of mercuric acetate (7 g) in water (10 ml) and THF (70 ml), and the mixture stirred for 2 h. Alkaline sodium borohydride (0.4 g in 20 ml of 3N NaOH) was then added to the ice-cooled reaction mixture and the organic layer separated. The aqueous layer was saturated with sodium chloride, extracted with ether and the combined extract dried. After removal of the solvent, the residue was chromatographed to get 5 (60%) (Found: C, 73.31; H, 13.61; N, 6.20. C₁₄H₂₇NO requires: C, 73.36; H, 13.53; N, 6.11%); δ 2.10 (1H, OH, D₂O exchangeable), 2.40–2.50 (4H, q, J 6 Hz, CH₂N(CH₂CH₂)₂) and 2.88 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, CH₂N(CH₂CH₂)₂).

N,N-Dimethyl-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-dichloromethyleneoctanylamine (6): To a stirred mixture of 1 (1.85 g), chloroform (2.4 ml) and triethylbenzylammonium chloride (0.04 g), was added aqueous 90% NaOH in portions during 5 min. Within 2 min an emulsion was formed and the temperature of the mixture increased slowly during 25 min to a maximum 50–60°. Thereafter, the temperature decreased and the colour changed. Chloroform layer was then separated and aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined ether extract was washed with 2M HCl followed by water. It was then dried, solvent removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to get 6 (75%, 1.38 g), b.p. 95–6°/3–4 mm (Found: C, 58.58; H, 9.42; N, 5.18. C₁₅H₂₅NCl₂ requires: C, 58.64; H, 9.39; N, 5.26%); δ 1.15–1.26 (12H, m, saturated methylenes, Cl₂C=C(CH₂)₂) and 2.36–2.43 (8H, m, CH₂N(CH₂)₂).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF COMPOUNDS (10–22) ON THE NUMBER OF ROOTS PER ROOTED SEGMENTS PRODUCED ON HYPOCOTYL CUTTINGS OF *V. radiata* AFTER 7 DAYS

Compd.	Concentration (g ml ⁻¹)			
	5	10	15	20
10	P	4.4±0.6	5.1±1.7	5.5±1.6
11	4.3±0.0	P	P	P
12	5.5±1.2	4.5±0.9	4.3±1.5	4.1±0.5
13	4.5±1.3	4.5±1.5	4.5±1.3	6.3±1.4
14	No rooting, inhibits the epicotyl elongation			
15	P	4.5±0.8	5.0±2.3	4.7±2.9
16	4.3±0.9	P	P	P
17	No rooting, inhibits the epicotyl elongation			
18	5.1±0.8	4.8±0.7	5.9±0.9	5.9±1.6
19	4.5±0.5	4.5±1.2	4.5±2.7	5.1±1.6
20	5.2±0.6	4.1±0.7	3.1±1.5	3.0±1.7
21	3.3±1.2	2.8±0.7	P	P
22	6.9±3.3	7.3±3.1	3.7±1.2	Toxic
Water (Control)	5.0±0.5			

*P = Primordials.

N,N-Diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-dichloromethyleno-octanylamine (7): It was prepared from the freshly distilled diethylamine (2; 2.12 g) as described above (Found: C, 61.18; H, 9.94; N, 4.67. C₁₅H₂₅NCl₂ requires: C, 61.22; H, 9.86; N, 4.76%); δ 1.03–1.23 (18H, m, N(CH₂CH₂)₂, (CH₂)₂CCl₂, saturated methylenes) and 2.40–2.50 (6H, CH₂N(CH₂CH₂)₂).

N,N-Dimethyl-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epoxyoctan-amine (8): To an ice-cold well-stirred solution of the amine (1; 500 mg) in methylene chloride (10 ml), perbenzoic acid (0.8*N*; 3.4 ml) in anhydrous methylene chloride (10 ml) was added dropwise over a period of 10 min. The reaction mixture was first stirred for 45 min at 0° and then at room temperature for 30 min. It was then poured into cold water and the organic layer separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether and the combined extract was washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried over fused calcium chloride, the solvent removed and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to get 8 (85%, 420 mg), b.p. 90–1/4–5 mm (Found: C, 72.41; H, 12.48; N, 6.94. C₁₂H₂₂NO requires: C, 72.36; H, 12.56; N, 7.03%); δ 1.23–1.3 (12H, m,

saturated methylenes, $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{HC} - \text{C} (\text{CH}_2)_2 \end{array}$, 2.30 (2H, t, *J* 6 Hz, CH₂-N(CH₂)₂) and 2.96 (1H, bs,

N,N-Diethyl-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-epoxyoctan-amine (9): It was prepared from 2 (500 mg) according to the procedure described above (Found: C, 74.10; H, 12.84; N, 6.21. C₁₄H₂₆NO requires: C, 74.00; H, 12.77; N, 6.16%); δ 1.06–1.26 (18H, m,

N(CH₂CH₂)₂, CH₂)₂ C - CH, saturated methylenes), 2.45–2.50 (16H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₂)₂) and 3.0 (1H, bs, (CH₂)₂C - CH).

General procedure for preparation of trialkylammonium iodides: 12 is shown as a typical run. To a cold (5°) solution of (7; 500 mg) in ether (15 ml) was added methyl iodide (0.2 g) slowly and the mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature. It was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight and the precipitate obtained by centrifugation afforded *N,N*-dimethyl-*N*-methyl-3,7-dimethyl-6,7-dichloromethyleneoctan-ylammonium iodide (12; 91%, 480 mg), m.p. 131°. All the quaternary salts of ammonia were prepared similarly by treating the different *N,N*-dialkylamine compounds with suitable alkyl iodides and the yield vary from 80 to 94%. The m.p. of compounds 11, 19, 21 and 22 were found to be 131, 138, 126 and 120°, respectively, and gave satisfactory elemental analyses. All other compounds were either hygroscopic in nature or thick oil.

References

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